

HIGH STRAIN RATE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SILICON CARBIDE REINFORCED ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

Brian M. Powers

Graduate Research Assistant

Jack R. Vinson

H. Fletcher Brown Professor of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering

Ian W. Hall

Associate Professor, Department of Mechanical Engineering and
Chair, Materials Science Program

University of Delaware
Mechanical Engineering
Newark, DE

Vincent Nardone

Senior Research Scientist

United Technologies Research Center
East Hartford, Connecticut

ABSTRACT

Composite materials offer excellent properties such as high specific strength and stiffness which make them attractive for many naval, aerospace and automotive applications. Even though they are candidate materials for many applications where high strain rate or ballistic impact loading is probable, little is known of the material responses to shock loading. Because mechanical properties vary significantly with strain rate, the use of static properties in the analysis and design of structures which undergo dynamic loadings can on one hand lead to a very conservative overweight design, or on the other hand can lead to designs which prematurely and unexpectedly fail. The use of quasi-static mechanical property data for high strain-rate load situations is at best misleading, and at worst could possibly be disastrous.

In the present paper, the results of a compression test program for a silicon carbide reinforced aluminum matrix composite are presented for strain rates up to 1033 sec^{-1} .

INTRODUCTION

At present, a program is underway at the University of Delaware under the Office of Naval Research sponsorship (Dr. Y.D.S. Rajapakse) that involves three tasks: (1) the high strain rate testing in compression and tension of various polymer matrix composite (and other) materials using the existing Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar facility, and correlation and analysis of the dynamic material properties obtained; (2) examination of all the samples tested, using optical and electron microscopy to characterize the deformation and fracture processes; and (3) the evaluation of the suitability of current models to describe the strength, deformation and failure of these models, or wherever necessary, the development of new models. It is necessary to learn more of the fundamental behavior of composites during failure caused by dynamic loading. Only then can a predictive capability be attained for existing materials, and better materials developed to withstand shock and other dynamic loads.

The Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar facility at the University of Delaware is described in Figure 1. Both transmission electron microscopes and scanning electron microscopes are being used in Phase 2. In Phase 3 the applicability of strength model equations such as Johnson-Cook, Ferilli-Armstrong, Steinberg-Guinan-Lund, and Bodner-Partom will be investigated and/or modified, since none of these are explicitly developed for composite materials.

In the SHPD equipment shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2, [1], impact is initiated by releasing nitrogen gas from pressurized chamber which causes the specimen to be impacted between the two bars. The striker bar is displaced on Teflon rings through the barrel where it strikes the incident bar (bar 1). The velocity of the striker bar V_{SB} just prior to impact is measured using two infrared beams set four inches apart.

Upon impact with the striker bar, the incident bar receives an elastic compressive strain wave with a wave velocity C_B and a wave shape $\epsilon_1(t)$ and is displaced along its length axis. This bar is guided by Teflon bearings which are bolted to a steel I beam and secured on a reinforced

Figure 1. University of Delaware SHPB Equipment

Figure 2. Lagrangian Diagram for the University of Delaware SHPB Equipment

concrete base to minimize any vibration. When the wave reaches the bar 1-specimen interface, a portion of the incident wave is reflected back into bar 1 as a tensile wave with a wave shape $\epsilon_R(t)$. The remaining portion is transmitted into the specimen as a compressive wave. The wave transmitted into the specimen travels through the specimen and reaches the specimen-bar 2 interface, where a portion of the wave is reflected back into the specimen as a tensile wave. The remaining portion is transmitted into bar 2 as a compressive wave with a wave shape $\epsilon_T(t)$. This bar is displaced similarly to bar 1 but is caught after the test by a simple dashpot.

Because the specimen length is short compared to the bar lengths, the initial stress wave in the specimen undergoes numerous internal reflections during the test. It is calculated that the initial wave duration in a typical specimen is approximately two microseconds. Within a composite material specimen, there may be differences in the speed of the wave in the fiber and matrix materials. For clarity, these specimen internal reflections are not shown in the Lagrangian diagram of the SHPB equipment shown in Figure 2 taken from [2]. Due to the numerous reflections, the stress distribution along the specimen length is smoothed out and the specimen is assumed to be in a uniform state of stress at any instant [3]. The Lagrangian diagram shows that there is a characteristic time window corresponding to the duration of the wave pulses. This is defined as the time it takes a wave to travel the length of the striker bar and back. For the University of Delaware SHPB, the wave pulse time window is approximately 290 microseconds. Thus, to record information accurately at specimen failure, the specimen must fail within 290 microseconds after the start of the test.

Strain gages are mounted on bars 1 and 2 equidistant from the specimen interfaces and are connected to the oscilloscope. A third strain gage, mounted on bar 1 near the striker bar, acts as a trigger for the oscilloscope. The oscilloscope records the strain gages output as voltage versus time curves. A disk drive is connected to the oscilloscope and can store the data on a floppy disk. Using this data, the stress and strain versus time of the specimen during the test can be calculated for the strain rate of that particular test.

In this paper, the concentration is on the compressive mechanical properties of silicon carbide particulate reinforced 2080 aluminum (20% particulate volume fraction) composite that is being used presently by the United Technologies Research Center. Because so little is known of the high strain rate mechanical properties and their modeling, it is logical to study materials of practical use, rather than materials of "academic" interest only.

This new data will add to what is now available for other materials. Zukas [1] shows that for many metals the mechanical properties vary significantly with strain rate. For composite material systems, there is relatively little data available. At Delaware, materials systems tested to date include E-glass/epoxy, glass/polyester, graphite/epoxy, Metton, carbon/glass, carbon/aluminum, and silicon carbide reinforced aluminum. These data were obtained by Finch, Choe and Frey [4,5,6] for their Master's theses. Later papers were published regarding this research by Choe, Finch and Vinson[7]; Frey, Vinson and Hall [8]; Frey, Vinson and Prewo [9], Newill and Vinson [10], and Powers, Vinson, Hall and Hubbard [11]. No attempt has been made to include other significant references herein, but merely to indicate experience of the authors through their previous research.

TEST RESULTS

The results of nine compression tests from material available are presented in Table 1. These tests were performed at ambient temperature, and the strain rates varied from 560 sec^{-1} to 1033 sec^{-1} . The data presented are grouped according to strain rate. The pressure column refers to the pressure of the nitrogen in the pressure chamber. The strain rate is calculated for each firing, and it is seen that although the pressure may be the same for various firings, the resulting strain rates may differ.

It is seen that for all firings these metal matrix composites did not fail. In each case the specimens yielded and a yield stress and strain were obtained. In addition a maximum stress and strain were also recorded, which at least indicates that the ultimate strength of the material exceeds that value for that strain rate given in Table 1.

The data of Table 1 are statistically analyzed in Table 2, which presents mean values and standard deviations for the material at these different strain rates.

It is interesting to see that even with these small sample sizes the standard deviation to mean value rates vary only from 1.34% to 5.90% for the strain rates; 2.18% to 10.8% for the yield stresses; 5.98% to 12.57% for the yield strains; and 2.31% to 14.1% for the moduli for elasticity. For the latter it is expected the standard deviation may be higher than the others because the modulus of elasticity is calculated by dividing the yield stress by the yield strain, and therefore not directly measured through the experiment.

For the present purpose, one defines the difference between two measured quantities to be significant if the mean value of one quantity falls outside the region of the mean ± 3 standard deviations of the other quantity.

It is seen that from Table 2, strain rates A and B are not significant from each other, but B is significantly different from C, and C is significantly different from A and B.

Concerning the yield stress the values for groups A and B are significantly different from each other, while B and C do not vary significantly from each other.

For the yield strain, A is significantly lower than B and C is significantly higher than B, because the standard deviation of the B group is so small.

For the modulus of elasticity, there is no significant difference among the three groups, and all modulus value are low compared to static values. This is a characteristic of Split Hopkinson Bar test results, so only the trends should be noted between SHPB tests at various strain rates.

From Table 2 it is seen that between strain rates of 592.4 sec^{-1} to 952.6 sec^{-1} , the yield stress of the material increases by 31.3%, while the yield strain increases by 68%. These are significant increases. Looking at Figure 3 and Figure 4, it is seen that the increases in yield stress and yield strain are linear with strain rate.

If one looks at the elastic strain energy over the increase in strain rate it is seen that it increases by 119% - defined as one half of the product of the yield stress and yield strain. That is most significant, and has major design implications. This can be contrasted with the strain energy to failure of the glass fiber polymer matrix composite of Reference 11 which remained constant over the range of stress rates from 151 sec^{-1} to 935.8 sec^{-1} , a comparable range.

CONCLUSIONS

For the SIC/2080 aluminum ($v_f = 20\%$) metal matrix composite in compression at ambient temperature, the following conclusions can be made:

1. The specimens did not fracture over the range of strain rates up 950 sec^{-1} , although compressive stresses exceeding 100,000 psi were attained at the high strain rate.
2. There are significant increases in yield stress with strain rate, such that the yield stress increases 31.3% and the yield strain increases 68% over the strain rate range tested.
3. The elastic strain energy for the material increases 119% from 592 sec^{-1} to 953 sec^{-1} .

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Table 1. Experimental Data for
SiC Particulate/2080 Al($V_f = 20\%$)

Group	Pressure (kPa)	Strain Rate (/sec)	Yield Stress (MPa)	Max Stress (MPa)	Yield Strain (mm/mm)	Max Strain (mm/mm)	Modulus (GPa)	Notes
A1	206.8	560.6	338.5	564.7	0.00785	0.12624	43.2	Specimens did not fail
A2	206.8	586.8	339.9	586.7	0.00880	0.12232	38.7	
A3	206.8	629.7	326.8	560.5	0.01008	0.12987	32.5	
B1	344.7	730.4	410.9	629.5	0.01169	0.18158	35.2	Max Stress and Strain are reported
B2	344.7	716.7	390.6	602.6	0.01075	0.18183	36.3	
C1	689.5	928.2	506.8	697.8	0.01485	0.27960	34.1	
C2	689.5	927.8	411.6	659.8	0.01670	0.28286	24.6	
C3	689.5	1033.3	426.8	689.5	0.01550	0.29435	27.5	
C4	482.6	921.2	402.0	619.2	0.01290	0.23011	31.2	

Table 2. Statistical Analysis for SiC Particulate/2080 Al ($V_f = 20\%$)

Group		Strain Rate (/sec)	Yield Stress (MPa)	Max Stress (MPa)	Yield Strain (mm/mm)	Max Strain (mm/mm)	Modulus (GPa)
A	Average	592.4	335.1	570.6	0.00891	0.12614	38.1
	St Dev	34.9	7.2	14.1	0.00112	0.00378	5.4
B	Average	723.6	400.8	616.1	0.01122	0.18171	35.8
	St Dev	9.7	14.4	19	0.00066	0.00018	0.8
C	Average	952.6	436.8	666.6	0.01499	0.27173	29.4
	St Dev	53.9	47.8	35.5	0.00159	0.02846	4.2

Figure 3. Yield Stress vs. Strain Rate

Figure 4. Yield Strain vs. Strain Rate